

Ascorbic acid has an anxiolytic-like effect in the presence of flumazenil in rats

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Abstract: Ascorbic acid (vitamin C) is a water-soluble vitamin; it is present in the highest concentration in the brain. Ascorbic acid in high doses acts as a potential treatment for various neuropathological and psychiatric conditions. Flumazenil is a benzodiazepine antagonist; it competitively inhibits the activity of benzodiazepine and non-benzodiazepine substances that interact with benzodiazepine receptors site on the GABA/benzodiazepine receptor complex. This study aims to investigate the effect of flumazenil on the anxiolytic action of ascorbic acid using an elevated plus maze model of anxiety in rats. Male Albino Wistar rats weighing between 250 and 320 grams were used. Rats were divided into four equal groups of seven rats each and treated as follows: Group I, the control group received a single dose of 1.0% tween 80; Group II treated with a single dose of 125 mg/kg ascorbic acid; Group III was injected by a single dose of 1.0 mg/kg flumazenil; Group IV received a combination treatment of 125 mg/kg ascorbic acid and 1.0 mg/kg flumazenil. Behavioural measurements using a plus maze were scored 30 min after the administration. The parameters scored are the time spent on the open and closed arms, the lines and number of entries into open and closed arms, and the anxiety measure. Ascorbic acid decreased anxiety measure and increased the total lines and total number of entries; this effect was abolished by the administration of flumazenil with ascorbic acid. Thus, ascorbic acid produces an anxiolytic-like effect in rats; this effect was abolished by flumazenil administration with ascorbic acid. This may indicate that the GABA/benzodiazepine receptor complex has to be stimulated to produce the anxiolytic effect.

Introduction

Ascorbic acid (AA, vitamin C) is a water-soluble vitamin; it reaches its highest concentration in the brain. AA has a neuroprotective function that acts as a cofactor in redox-coupled reactions essential for synthesizing neurotransmitters. AA in high doses has a potential treatment for various neuropathological and psychiatric conditions [1]; it is a necessary nutrient in human diets, and its deficiency results in scurvy disease [2]. Recent research confirms the antioxidant role of AA in preventing oxidative stress injury in the brain [3]. AA has been suggested to play a role in mood regulation [4]. In the previous work, it was found that AA produced dose-dependent anxiolytic effects without sedation in doses up to 500 mg/kg in rats. It was clear that the acute administration of AA was accompanied by increased gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) levels in almost all brain areas leading to anxiolytic action. It has been suggested that AA may act as a partial allosteric modulator

of the GABA_A receptor since it induces a smaller response in their target cells than a full allosteric modulator such as alprazolam. In addition, acute administration of AA (125 or 500 mg/kg), selectively increases the ascorbate levels in the striatum, mid-brain, and cerebral cortex [5].

Flumazenil (Ro15-1788) is an imidazobenzodiazepine, developed by Hoffmann la Roche in the 1980s [6]. Flumazenil is a competitive benzodiazepine antagonist; it competitively inhibits the activity of benzodiazepine and non-benzodiazepine substances that interact with benzodiazepine receptors site on the GABA/benzodiazepine receptor complex. It can also reverse the binding of benzodiazepines to benzodiazepine receptors [7]. On the other hand, it does not reverse the effects of other GABAergic sedative-hypnotics such as barbiturates, inhalational anesthetics, propofol, or ethanol, nor does it reverse the effects of opioids [8]. Flumazenil is used in benzodiazepine overdose emergencies. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-approved clinical uses for flumazenil include reversal agents for benzodiazepine overdose and postoperative sedation from benzodiazepine anaesthetics [9]. Thus, this study aims to investigate the effect of flumazenil on the anxiolytic action of AA using an elevated plus-maze model of anxiety in rats.

Materials and methods

Animals: Adult male Albino Wistar rats weighing between 250 and 320 g, bred in the local animal house of the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Tripoli, Libya were used. The rats were housed in an animal house under controlled conditions (20-25°C and 12/12-hr light/dark cycle). Rats received free access to a standard pellet diet (Beeky company-Austria) and water *ad libitum*.

Chemical administration: Throughout the studies described in this work, rats were randomly assigned to receive different treatments. Acute drug administration was performed by intraperitoneal route, 1.0% of tween 80 (Riedel-De Haen AG Seelze Hanover, Germany) was used as a suspending agent [10], and all control rats were injected with the vehicle. A volume of injection of 1.0 ml/kg of body weight was adopted in all the experiments [11].

Experimental design: Rats were divided into four equal groups of seven rats each and treated as follows: Group I, the control group received a single dose of 1.0% tween 80; Group II, treated with a dose of 125 mg/kg AA (Weishing Pharmaceutical Company, Shijiazhuang, Korea); Group III, injected by a dose of 1.0 mg/kg flumazenil (F. Hoffmann-la Roche Company, Switzerland); Group IV, received a combination of 125 mg/kg AA and 1.0 mg/kg flumazenil. Behavioural measurements using a plus maze were scored 30 min after drug administration. The total time of the test is 240 sec. The methodology and handling of rats were according to the guidelines of animal use of the University of Tripoli, Tripoli, Libya [UOT, 2017].

Behavioural measurements using elevated plus maze: The wooden elevated plus-maze (EPM) apparatus consists of two open arms (45×10 cm each) and two opposite closed arms of the same size, with walls of 40 cm in height. The arms are linked by a central square (10×10 cm). The maze was suspended 50 cm from the room floor, causing aversive stimuli to the rats in the open arms [12]. The rat should be exposed to the plus maze only once after the treatment, otherwise, the anxiolytic-like effects are considerably reduced by pre-exposure to the maze [13, 14]. This phenomenon is known as "one-trial tolerance" [15]. It was found that pre-exposure alters behavioral and pharmacological responses in the EPM [16, 17]. The EPM test was conducted in a closed room with a low illumination [18]. The test was performed between 8:00 am and 4:00 pm, under constant conditions. Rats were placed on the central part of the maze facing the closed arm. The number of entries, lines crossed, and the time spent on the open and closed arms were scored over four min. An entry is defined as having both forepaws on the respective arm. The line crossing is defined as both forepaws crossing the line [16]. Anxiety measure (A.M.) was calculated by dividing the total time spent on closed arms by the total test time; when the rat suffers fear and anxiety, the A.M. ratio is close to 1.0 [19, 20].

Statistical analysis: Kolmogorov-Smirnov maximum deviation test for goodness of fit to determine whether the observed samples were parametric. If the parameters are normally distributed, the difference among groups is analyzed using one-way ANOVA, followed by a post-hoc test (Duncan and LSD). If the parameters of samples were nonparametric, treatments were compared by applying the Mann-Whitney two samples (non-matched) test. The statistical difference was considered to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

In **Table 1**, Ascorbic acid at a dose of 125 mg/kg produced a significant decrease in the anxiety measure ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the control-treated group ($p \leq 0.05$); while the administration of flumazenil alone treated group (1.0 mg/kg) or flumazenil combined with AA did not change the anxiety measure compared to the control treated group ($p > 0.05$). Administration of AA significantly increases the time spent on open arms and zero area compared to the control treated group ($p \leq 0.05$). At the same time, it significantly decreases the time spent on closed arms compared to the control-treated group ($p \leq 0.05$). Administration of flumazenil alone or in combination with AA did not show any change in the time spent on closed, open arms, and zero area, compared to the control-treated group ($p > 0.05$) (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Effect of acute administration of flumazenil and ascorbic acid on anxiety measure and time spent on the arms of the plus maze

Treatments	Anxiety measure (AM)	Time spent on open arms (min)	Time spent on closed arms (min)	Time spent on zero area (min)
1.0% tween 80 (5.0 ml/kg)	1.00±0.0	0.00±0.00	240.0±00.0	0.00±0.00
Ascorbic acid (125 mg/kg)	0.551±0.140 *	71.0± 5.92 *	132.29±33.63 *	36.71±17.81 *
Flumazenil (1.0 mg/kg)	0.981±0.015	0.00±0.00	236.14±02.49	3.86±2.49
Ascorbic acid & Flumazenil	0.983±0.010 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^a	235.57±3.66 ^a	4.43±3.66 ^a

The values are the means±S.E, * Significantly different from tween 80 treated group at $p \leq 0.05$,

^a Significantly different from the ascorbic acid 125 mg/kg treated group at $p \leq 0.05$

In **Table 2**, rats treated with AA significantly increased the lines crossed on open arms, and the number of entries into open arms also increased the total number of entries compared to the control-treated group ($p \leq 0.05$). While lines crossed on closed arms, total lines crossed, and number of entries into closed arms were not changed after the administration of AA compared to the control treated group ($p > 0.05$). Treatment with flumazenil alone or combined with AA did not change the lines crossed and the number of entries into a different compartment, even the total lines crossed and the total number of entries was not changed compared to the control treated group ($p > 0.05$) (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Effect of acute administration of flumazenil and ascorbic acid on the lines crossed and number of entries into the arms of the plus maze

Treatments	Lines crossed number			Number of entries number		
	Open arms	Closed arm	Total lines crossed	Open arms	Closed arms	Total entries
1.0% Tween 80 (5.0 ml/kg)	0.00±0.00	5.43±1.15	5.43±1.15	0.00±0.00	1.00±0.00	1.00±0.00
Ascorbic acid (125 mg/kg)	3.14±1.08 *	4.00±0.82	7.14±1.32	1.14±0.26 *	1.00±0.22	2.14±0.34 *
Flumazenil (1.0 mg/kg)	0.00±0.00	4.00±0.69	4.00±0.69	0.00±0.00	1.14±0.14	1.14±0.14
Ascorbic acid & Flumazenil	0.0±0.00 ^a	6.43±1.62	6.43±1.62	0.0±0.00 ^a	1.29±0.18	1.29±0.18 ^a

The values are the means±S.E, * Significantly different from tween 80 treated group at $p \leq 0.05$,

^a Significantly different from the ascorbic acid 125 mg/kg treated group at $p \leq 0.05$

Discussion

Anxiety is a chronic severe psychiatric disorder. Thus, several anxiety disorders are highly prevalent and chronic disorders with treatment resistance to current pharmacotherapies occurring in about one in three patients [21, 22]. In the CNS, the major mediators of anxiety disorders are noradrenaline, serotonin, dopamine, and GABA. Peptides, as corticotropin-releasing factors, may also be involved in the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis [23]. Dysfunction of the GABA system activity has been associated with anxiety disorders, and modulation of the GABA system can result in anxiolysis or anxiogenesis [12, 24]. The positive modulators of GABA_A receptors result in anxiolysis and the negative modulators produce an anxiogenic effect [25]. AA is considered an important vitamin that can be used to manage all kinds of stressful conditions that are linked to inflammatory processes and immunity [26]. AA has some other beneficial effects on the management of psychiatric disorders [27], including depression [28, 29], anxiety and schizophrenia, and neurodegenerative diseases [30]. AA has strong antioxidant properties [31, 32] and it increases superoxide dismutase (SOD) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) effects in the brain. The administration of AA also increases the serum level of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) [33].

In the current study, 125 mg/kg of AA produced an anxiolytic-like effect by decreasing the anxiety measure in the elevated plus maze. Thus, the rat spent more time on open arms, an increased number of entries into open arms, and less time on closed arms compared to the control-treated group. It was demonstrated that the pharmacological investigation confirmed that the approach of the open arms was specifically increased by classical anxiolytics such as chlordiazepoxide and diazepam and decreased by anxiogenic substances such as yohimbine, caffeine, and amphetamine [34]. AA is a water-soluble vitamin that has a high concentration in the brain tissue under normal conditions [33]. Ascorbate distribution within different brain areas suggests that it has an important role in the brain. Ascorbate is considered a neuromodulator of glutamatergic, dopaminergic, cholinergic, and GABAergic transmission and related behaviours [35]. Further, AA at 0.5 mM concentration exhibits a neuroprotective effect through interaction with the GABA_B receptor [36]. While another finding indicated that AA exerts an anti-depressant effect in mice at a concentration of 1.0 mg/kg, possibly by interacting with GABA_A and GABA_B receptors [37]. In the human body, AA may act as an endogenous ligand that can potentiate GABA neurotransmission in the CNS [38]. The GABA receptor is the most essential target, to produce anxiolytic and/or antidepressant effects [23]. AA binds to the active sites of GABA_{A2}, GABA_{A5}, GABA_{B1}, and GABA_{B2} proteins [39]. In the rat brain cortical synaptosome, AA stimulates GABA binding capacity [40]. The binding affinities of AA were -5.0, -5.5, and -5.3 kcal/mol with GABA_{A2}, GABA_{B1}, and GABA_{B2}, respectively [39]. AA showed moderate binding affinities with GABA receptor subunits, including GABA_{A2}, B₁, and B₂, respectively [39].

Sedative and anxiolytic agents such as benzodiazepine (BZ) exert their action through GABA upon the GABA_A receptor [41]. Classical BZs bind to GABA_A receptors containing α_1 , α_2 , α_3 , and/or α_5 subunits, while binding affinity to α_4 -containing and α_6 -containing subunits is extremely weak [42]. The GABA_A receptor α_1 subunit is associated with sedation, whereas the GABA_A receptor α_2 and α_3 subunits are involved in anxiolytic effects [43, 44]. Genetic and pharmacological studies suggested that the major role of the α_2 and the α_3 GABA_A receptor subunit is in mediating anxiolysis [42, 45, 46]. It is found that AA at higher doses (10^{-3} M) markedly inhibits, and at lower doses (10^{-6} M) highly stimulates 3H-GABA binding capacity in the rat brain cortical synaptosomes [40, 47]. It seems that the AA dose used in this study is considered low dose leading to stimulation of GABA binding capacity and producing an anxiolytic effect. In this work, flumazenil is used to investigate the possible mechanism of action of AA as an anxiolytic agent in rats. Flumazenil is best known as a competitive antagonist at the B-binding site on the GABA_A receptor and has long-standing clinical use as an emergency treatment for BZ overdose [48, 49]. It is essentially used as an antidote in the treatment of BZ overdoses [50]. Two sub-types of BZ receptors were identified; namely, BZR₁ was found through the brain,

predominantly in the cerebellum, while BZR₂ is located principally in the cortex, hippocampus, and spinal cord. Compounds with selectivity towards the BZR₁ subtype would be non-sedative anxiolytics, and in contrast, BZR₂ selective compounds might be non-anxiolytic sedatives [51].

In this study, the administration of flumazenil alone in a dose of 1.0 mg/kg did not change the anxiety measure or the spontaneous motor activity compared to the control-treated group. Therefore, flumazenil represents a competitive antagonist blocking the enhancing effect of agonists and the depressant effect of "inverse agonists" on GABAergic synaptic transmission [52]. Flumazenil was originally reported to lack effects on behaviour when given on its own, although it was later found to possess some 'anxiogenic' activity [9, 53]. Flumazenil administration alone in a dose of 1.0 mg/kg did not change the time spent on any areas. Flumazenil has no or only weak intrinsic efficacy for changing the GABAergic transmission [52]. It has weak intrinsic agonist activity on the GABA_AR [49, 54]; but depending on basal conditions, tests, dosage, and measurements performed. Flumazenil had weak agonist-like and weak inverse agonist-like properties [55]. Therefore, it has no or only weak effects when given to animals or humans, but can inhibit the effects of BZ receptor agonists and inverse BZ receptor agonists [52]. Weak intrinsic agonist-like or inverse agonist-like pharmacological activity of flumazenil is unlikely to be of clinical importance [55]. According to the previous explanation, flumazenil did not change the anxiety measure or the spontaneous motor activity with the dose used. This study revealed that the anxiolytic action of AA in the EPM was abolished by the administration of flumazenil. According to a model in mice, flumazenil antagonizes the anxiolytic effect of BZs [56]. It may act by binding to the CNS BZ receptors and competitively blocks BZ activation of inhibitory GABAergic synapses. Also, flumazenil can inhibit the enhancement of GABA currents [49]. Administration of flumazenil with AA decreased significantly the time spent on open arms and increased the anxiety measure significantly when compared with the AA alone treated group. The present findings suggested that AA as an endogenous ligand can potentiate GABA neurotransmission in the CNS [37]; it may stimulate GABA binding capacity [39]. At the same time, BZR₁ has to be stimulated by endogenous benzodiazepine for AA to produce its anxiolytic effect. Endogenous BZ of natural origin has been found in human blood and brains as well as in medicinal plants and foods; it acts as an agonist at the BZ receptors of central type. It is considered a natural anxiolytic and sedative [57]. These compounds could act as physiological regulators of the GABA_A receptors [58]. AA could produce an anxiolytic effect through stimulation of GABA neurotransmission. Flumazenil abolishes the effect of AA, through blocking the BZR. This effect of flumazenil will block BZ activation of inhibitory GABAergic synapses, leading to antagonizing the anxiolytic effect of AA.

Conclusion: Ascorbic acid produces an anxiolytic-like effect in rats, using an elevated plus maze model of anxiety; this effect was abolished by flumazenil administration with ascorbic acid. This indicates that the GABA/benzodiazepine receptor complex has to be stimulated to produce the anxiolytic effect.

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